

THE ROLE OF THE YOUTH UNION PRIMARY ORGANIZATION IN INCREASING THE LEGAL CULTURE OF YOUTH IN SOCIETY

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ANNOTATION

This article describes the role of the Youth Union Primary organization in the formation of high legal culture in society as one of the most pressing issues, in the formation of which young people, in general, all segments of citizens, achieve legal literacy, have a high level of legal consciousness and can apply their legal knowledge in everyday life.

Keywords: Constitution, corruption, legal information, infringement legal consciousness and legal culture.

Introduction

As one of the most pressing issues of today, there will be no exaggeration to say the formation of a high legal culture in society. To achieve civil society, citizens need to be well aware of their rights and freedoms. Zero human rights and fundamental freedoms are among the leading principles of international law. Therefore, in today's developed world, many countries have praised internationally accepted human rights documents on ensuring human rights and freedoms, Security, living conditions. And the non-deviant observance of these documents depends on the extent to which the legal culture of citizens is formed.

Legal culture is people's level of legal knowledge, conscious attitude towards law, respect for law and compliance with it. Legal culture is an integral part of the general culture of society. Therefore, legal culture means the legal life of the society, its legal events, normative and legal documents, the system of moral, ethical and legal values that represents the level achieved in the development of legal consciousness, as well as obedience to the law that is decided in accordance with it, and legal order in the country. to establish is understood as the implementation of regulation of social relations.

In particular, in the promotion of legal culture, first of all, the work on legal education and upbringing is systematic and continuous, for many years this issue has been considered as the work of law enforcement agencies and some government bodies, in order to ensure sufficient participation of other institutions of the family, neighborhood and civil society, in addition, the formation of legal immunity, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 PF-5618 "on the fundamental improvement of the system for the promotion of legal consciousness and legal culture in society" serves as the basis for increasing demand and responsibility in a new way in order to approach the work of awakening a sense of intolerance to violations.

In addition, to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On organizational measures to further improve the activities of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated April 13, 2018 No. PQ-3666 and the state and economy in order to create a system of training legal personnel in narrow and specialized specialties that are in high demand in administrative bodies, as well as to improve the quality of professional legal education,³ Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 858 of

October 23, 2018 In accordance with the decision of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Azerbaijan on measures to organize training in legal technical schools⁴, the establishment of one - 14 legal technical schools in each region within the structure of the Ministry of Justice will serve not only to improve the legal knowledge of young people, but also to provide them with mature professional education.

According to its basic essence and philosophy, our constitution has put forward the idea that the greatest of all worldly blessings is the human being.

A necessary condition for building a legal state and civil society is the unconditional implementation of laws. Uniform and unconditional implementation of laws depends on the attitude of our jurists to their duties and their sense of responsibility.

Raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of young people, raising them in the spirit of respect for laws is one of the important issues facing our country at the same time that education of the young generation growing up in our country has risen to the level of state policy. The development of a legal democratic state and the development of society depends on the high level of education and legal literacy of the growing generation.

A competent generation with a good education does not enter the street of any offense, does not sink into its swamps. But, it is sad that today many of the teenagers who got into this street are sucked.

At the beginning of the matter, we began to talk about youth. Who do we mean by "youth"?

According to Article 4 of the law "on the basics of State Youth Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", adopted by the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 20, 1991, state youth policy is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this law and other legislation that regulates social, economic and Foreign Relations related to the interests of young people.

This law defines the main basis of state policy, which applies to citizens between the ages of 14 and 30, and recognizes it as the basis for the development of relevant laws and their introduction into the system.

If the International Treaty of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes rules that are different from those in this law and in other legislation on the state youth policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the provisions of the international treaty apply.

So, by youth, in a general sense, it is possible to understand individuals between the ages of 14 and 30.

Starting from the first days when our country achieved independence, human rights, its dignity were raised as a first-class issue, and all legal foundations were created and created. In this regard, the head and government of our country also assigned a number of important tasks to the employees of law enforcement agencies. In particular, the bodies and institutions of justice are entrusted with ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, restoring their violated rights, responsibly approaching citizens' appeals. In addition, another of the main functions of the offices of justice is to elevate the legal culture in society.

It should be noted that the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, feeling this important issue, has committed to the effective use of all acceptable methods of propaganda. Over the past two years, we can cite as proof of our word several projects developed and implemented in order to raise the legal culture in society, to further increase the legal literacy of the population, especially young people. One of these projects is the activities of the "legal advocacy group", consisting of young lawyers, formed in 2009 under the Ministry of Justice. To date, meetings with more than 62,000 young men and girls have been held by this group in about 70 remote districts of our country to raise their legal literacy. This brochure was

created on the basis of the interests of young people, their thoughts, suggestions and reflections during legal propaganda events.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In addition, young people and all layers of citizens can achieve legal literacy, have a high level of legal awareness and increase their legal literacy, in order to quickly and clearly convey the content of legal documents to the general population, they can apply their legal knowledge in everyday life, and to increase legal awareness and legal culture among young people. , in particular, an effective mechanism of cooperation of educational institutions with law enforcement bodies has been developed to promote in their minds that corruption is a very negative evil for the development of society and the country, to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of the young generation. Based on this, the Ministry of Justice's holding of the "National Constitutional Examination" this year was of great importance in the understanding and implementation of the rights and obligations enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is no exaggeration to say that the participation of more than 50,000 citizens (53% of them are men, 47% of them are women), 61% of the participants are young people, and the oldest citizen is 71 years old.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-443 of September 7, 2017 "On Dissemination of Legal Information and Ensuring its Use"⁵ is aimed at increasing the legal literacy of the population, making the content of legal documents quick and understandable to the general population. It is of great importance in the prevention of various offenses among young people, as well as in the regulation of relations in the field of distribution of legal information and provision of its use.

On the basis of the concept "high legal culture – guarantee of the development of the country", a number of works are carried out on the principle of "person – family – neighborhood – Educational Institution – Organization – Society" in order to raise legal consciousness and legal culture in society so that all segments of the population can achieve legal literacy, have a high level of legal Within the framework of the above laws, resolutions and decrees, when face-to-face dialogue and meetings with representatives of the navqiran generation are organized and their problems are studied, we witness an increased interest of the population in our laws, legal issues.

Law is not just a part of a common culture, but the basis of its core, base. Legal culture refers to the fact that the basis of law of each state is the existence of legal norms, the knowledge of the existing laws of citizens and their observance in their activities – an important condition for the establishment of a legal and Democratic state is understood in civil society the mature spirituality of people, their legal duty and responsibilities. From Jumala, it should be noted that in increasing the legal culture of society, we can achieve even more results if the level of legal knowledge in higher education itself is aimed at further accelerating the organization of participation in practical processes, for example, in the direction of "national beauty, fundamentals of spirituality and legal education". It is absolutely true that it is impossible to look at the leprosy of the legal culture of young people and their legal education as consisting only in the acquisition of a number of knowledge about the criteria and principles of current law documents.

More than 60% of the population of Uzbekistan is made up of young people under the age of 30, and the close connection of our country with how they are formed today requires serious attention to representatives of the younger generation.

Conclusion

The purpose of the legal education of young people and their legal culture is to form obedience to the law and respect of the law of the individual. Respect for the law does not imply to legal institutions that they simply make an idea in relation to the individual as external guidelines and prohibitions, but to a continuous perception of them as values that correspond to one another of society with the individual. After all, legal culture and spirituality are components of universal values.

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